

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Report for Deliverables/Milestones

Document info

Title	Presentation of New Charts of the TMD Data for TrP F2F
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Abbreviations and Acronyms

TMD	Training Metrics Database
TrP	Training Platform

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Executive Summary

This milestone reports on the updated version of the TMD database model and potential new charts, as presented during the TrP face-to-face meeting (slides [here](#)). The new data model allows for Node specific questions and visualizations, which increases usability of the TMD, both within and outside of ELIXIR. With the potential for custom questions, all reporting can now be done directly from TMD. The update to the data model also allows for updates to the ELIXIR core questions in a smoother way. This update was integral to the continued development of the TMD within the ELIXIR 2024-2028 Scientific Programme.

Presentation Overview

The updated TMD data model and example visualizations were presented at the TrP face-to-face meeting on March 27, 2025. The session highlighted the updated data model and demonstrated examples of charts that could be generated by this.

New Question sets

The questions sets now consists of:

1. **Event metrics:** Specifying the metadata of the event. Has not been updated in the new model.
2. **Quality, Demographics and Impact metrics:** Charts depicting the quality and impact of training sessions on participants, including pre- and post-training assessments. These metrics are now represented differently in the database, and can be fully updated when updating the ELIXIR core questions.
3. **Node specific metrics:** Node administrators can now create their own custom question sets in the TMD by using this option. Uploaded answers will be displayed alongside other metrics.

Node specific questions (examples)

Reports

[World map](#)
[Events](#)
[Impact](#)
[Demographic](#)
[Quality](#)
[Swedish node questions](#)
[Browse events](#)
[Upload data](#)
[Import from TeSS](#)
[All institutions](#)

Date from:
 Date to:
 Type:

Funding
 ELIXIR Converge
 EOSC Life
 EXCELERATE
 ELIXIR Implementation Study
 ELIXIR Community / Use case
 ELIXIR Node
 ELIXIR Hub
 ELIXIR Platform
 Non-ELIXIR / Non-EXCELERATE Funds

Target audience
 Academia/ Research Institution
 Industry
 Non-Profit Organisation
 Healthcare

Additional platforms
 Compute
 Data
 Interoperability
 Tools
 NA

Node only
 Node only

Chart type
 Pie chart Bar chart

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How did you experience the hybrid setting?

Option	Number of responses
Worked really well	2
A bit hard to connect to everyone	1
I would prefer to not have hybrid	1

How did you experience the hybrid setting?

Have you taken any other NBIS courses?

Option	Number of responses
Tools for reproducible research	2
Omics Integration	1
scRNAseq analysis	1
No, this is the first one	0
Introduction to NGS	0

Have you taken any other NBIS courses?

What cities do you think we should have more courses in?

Option	Number of responses
Uppsala	2
Umeå	2
Stockholm	0
Lund	0

What cities do you think we should have more courses in?

Outcomes and Impacts of the deliverable

The change of the database model has great impact on the continuing work specified in the Work programme:

- Allows for updates to the ELIXIR core questions
- Improves usability for nodes by uploading node specific questions
- Prepares for future work of connecting the TMD to other systems using an API as per the work programme
- Improves reach outside ELIXIR when the TMD now is flexible enough to support not only ELIXIR questions